

SEARCH FOR NEW INSECTICIDES. PART XI. SYNTHESIS OF SUBSTITUTED $\omega\omega$ -DICHLOROACETOPHENONES

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Several alkyl- and halogen-substituted phenolic esters of dichloroacetic acid and the corresponding *o*-hydroxy- $\omega\omega$ -dichloroacetophenones have been prepared with a view to studying their insecticidal activity.

It has been observed by Tiwari and Tripathi (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 214) that phenolic esters of chloroacetic acid as well as the *o*-hydroxy- ω -chloroacetophenones derived from them are very active against house fly. Dormal, Delvaux and Dills (*J. Econ. Entomol.*, 1950, 43, 915) have found that chlorination of phenols increases their insecticidal efficiency. We have therefore prepared a number of phenolic esters of dichloroacetic acid and *o*-hydroxy- $\omega\omega$ -dichloroacetophenones by the Fries migration of these esters. The ketonic and the ester groupings present in these compounds being lipophilic and the hydroxy grouping, hydrophilic in nature, the esters and the phenolic ketones are expected to possess insecticidal activity (Lauger *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1944, 27, 918).

The phenolic esters of dichloroacetic acid were prepared in the usual way by refluxing the appropriate phenols and dichloroacetyl chloride in benzene in presence of dry magnesium (Spasov, *Ann. Univ. Sofia*, II, Faculte phys-maths., 1938-39, 2, 35, 289). The phenolic ketones were obtained by the Fries rearrangement of the above esters in the absence of a solvent, using 1.2 to 1.7 moles of anhydrous aluminium chloride. These ketones were characterised through their 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones.

The insecticidal activity of sixteen of these esters and hydroxyketones has been determined exclusively against laboratory-bred flies (*M. domestica*) using the topical method of application by a micrometer syringe. Some of these compounds show appreciable insecticidal activity, though inferior to the standard insecticides like D D T, when tested under identical conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL

Phenolic Esters of Dichloroacetic Acid.—To the appropriate phenol (0.1 M) in 20-25 c.c. of anhydrous benzene clean and dry magnesium ribbon in the form of a spiral was added. Dichloroacetyl chloride (0.1 M) was then added dropwise and the mixture was refluxed on the water-bath until HCl had ceased to evolve. The completion of the reaction took nearly 10 to 12 hours. After cooling, water was added and the benzene layer separated. It was then washed with 1% NaOH solution and finally with water. The benzene extract was dried over anhydrous calcium chloride and the benzene removed by distillation. The residual oil was distilled under reduced pressure. The esters, thus obtained, are summarised in Table I.

TABLE I

Substituted phenyl dichloroacetates.	B. P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1. <i>o</i> -Chloro-	129°/1 mm.	75 %	C ₈ H ₇ O ₂ Cl ₃	40.01	40.08	2.01	2.08
2. 2:4-Dichloro-	125°/2	86	C ₈ H ₄ O ₂ Cl ₄	34.80	35.04	1.08	1.41
3. 2-Chloro-3- <i>tert.</i> -butyl-	173°/4	71	C ₁₂ H ₁₈ O ₂ Cl ₃	47.89	48.73	3.96	4.93
4. 3:5-Dimethyl-	120°/4	76	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ Cl ₂	50.98	51.50	3.96	4.33
5. 3-Ethyl-	126°/2	81	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ Cl ₂	50.76	51.50	3.87	4.33
6. 2- <i>tert.</i> -Butyl-5-methyl-	145°/3	66	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₂ Cl ₂	55.77	56.70	5.08	5.81
7. 4- <i>tert.</i> -Butyl-	130°/8	76	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ Cl ₂	54.96	55.17	5.04	5.36
8. 4- <i>tert.</i> -Amyl-	140°/2	73	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₂ Cl ₂	55.56	56.70	5.17	5.81
9. 4- <i>sec.</i> -Amyl-	135°/4	74	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₂ Cl ₂	56.08	57.70	5.75	5.81
10. 3-Methoxy-	139°/3	76	C ₉ H ₉ O ₂ Cl ₂	40.96	41.70	2.98	3.40

Fries Rearrangement of the Esters.—The appropriate ester (1.0 *M*) was taken in a 500 c.c. round-bottomed flask, fitted with a reflux condenser and a calcium chloride guard tube. Finely powdered AlCl₃ (anhyd, 1.2 *M*) was added to it and the mixture was heated in an oil-bath at 120° for ½ hour. On decomposing the resultant puffy mass with ice and dilute HCl, an oil separated out (solids in the case of two esters which were filtered and recrystallised from hot alcohol). It was taken up in ether, washed successively with water, 1% sodium carbonate solution and finally with water. The ethereal layer was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the ether removed by distillation. The residual oil was distilled under reduced pressure. The hydroxyketones obtained conformed to Pyman's test (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 280).

These ketones obtained were all converted into 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones, which were recrystallised from hot glacial acetic acid. The b.p., m.p., yield and percentage of nitrogen of the compounds so obtained are recorded in Table II,

TABLE II

Substituted <i>o</i> -hydroxyl- dichloroacetophenones.	B. P.	Yield.	M. P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Calc.
1. 3-Chloro-	173°/8 mm.	76%	160°	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₄ O ₅ Cl ₃	10.33	10.96
2. 3:5-Dichloro-	(m.p.) 90°	50	149°	C ₁₄ H ₅ N ₄ O ₅ Cl ₄	11.97	12.44
3. 3-Chloro-5- <i>tert.</i> -butyl-	175°/20	79	130°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₅ Cl ₃	11.15	11.77
4. 4:6-Dimethyl-	150°/4	58	145°	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₅ Cl ₂	12.87	13.55
5. 5-Ethyl-	110°/8	53	230°	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₅ Cl ₂	12.84	13.55
6. 3- <i>tert.</i> -Butyl-6-methyl-	88°/6	60	145°	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₅ Cl ₂	11.94	12.30
7. 5- <i>tert.</i> -Butyl-	120°/10	86	150°	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₅ Cl ₂	11.84	12.73
8. 5- <i>tert.</i> -Amyl-	122°/2	54	140°	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₅ Cl ₂	11.96	12.31
9. 5- <i>sec.</i> -Amyl-	125°/10	43	145°	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₅ Cl ₂	11.97	12.31
10. 4-Methoxy-	(m.p.) 84°	42	201°	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₅ Cl ₂	12.98	13.49

Bioassay of the Insecticidal Action.—Compounds recorded in Table III were tested for contact insecticidal activity against laboratory-bred house flies (*M. domestica*) in the following way :

A solution of the compound (10%) was made in acetone and applied topically to house flies (4-6 days old) with a microsyringe. A volume of 0.001 c.c. was applied to each fly on its back. After treatment the flies were transferred to a wire-mesh cage and held for observation. The rate of mortality was estimated according to Abbot's formula. Details of the experiments are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

No. of flies taken = 25. Dose per individual = 0.001 ml.

	Mortality after 24 hrs.	Corrected percentage.		Mortality after 24 hrs.	Corrected percentage
Phenyl dichloroacetates:			<i>o</i> -Hydroxy- <i>o,o</i> -dichloroacetophenones.		
2-Chloro-	12	46	3-Chloro-	10	37
2:4-Dichloro-	10	37	3-Chloro-5- <i>tert.</i> -butyl-	13	52
2-Chloro-4- <i>tert.</i> -butyl-	5	24	4:6-Dimethyl-	17	56
3:5-Dimethyl-	4	...	5-Ethyl-	18	70
3-Ethyl-	5	24	3- <i>tert.</i> -Butyl-6-methyl-	13	50
5-Methyl-3- <i>tert.</i> -butyl-	8	22	5- <i>tert.</i> -Amyl-	10	37
4- <i>tert.</i> -Butyl-	13	50	5- <i>tert.</i> -Butyl-	6	20
4- <i>tert.</i> -Amyl-	11	42	5- <i>sec.</i> -Amyl-	10	37
			D D T	25	100

The authors wish to thank the Director, Central Laboratories for Scientific and Industrial Research, Hyderabad for kindly permitting the bioassay of these insecticides done in his laboratory and Dr. M. B. Naidu of the above laboratory for carrying out the bioassay.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
UNIVERSITY OF LUCKNOW,
LUCKNOW.

Received May 5, 1955.